

The 8-Queens Puzzle

(not only is the board larger but also some queens have already placed)

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Abstract

How does placing the queens on the $n \times n$ board?

This article demonstrates how a close relationship between one rule and another, for each side of the board and is approximate, in theory, can be shown that the problem is not of the NP-Complete type.

Introduction

Let's take a 7x7 solution (of odd number (7 in this case)). The operation is very simple, you take the central line or rather the half of the board and you place all the queens on the same line, you can see that above and below are 3 lines and 7 empty columns, simply proceed with the calculation $7 \times 7 = 49$, $49/2 = 24.5$, $24/2 = 12$, we now know that the queens will move a total of 12 squares, namely 6 spaces above and 6 spaces below, and only one queen will remain stationary on the central row, one very important thing is that if a queen moves two spaces under it there will be another one that moves two spaces above so that every queen has her twin but only the central queen will be singular, so let's count the empty spaces on each alternating column.

We note in the figure (Fig. 1.1) that there are always two opposite queens:

Above Q-1 and below Q-1 (Q-1 = 1 movement)

Above Q-2 and below Q-2 (Q-2 = 2 movements)

Above Q-3 and below Q-3 (Q-3 = 3 movements)

In the middle only a queen Q-0 (Q-0 = 0 movements)

and the sum of the above moves is 6 and below is 6 which is exactly 12 movements in all and another very important thing to notice is that this rule applies to all 4 sides of the board, so there are 6 movements on the right and 6 movements on the left and 6 movements on the bottom and 6 movements on the top.

Fig. 1.1

					Q-3	
			Q-2			
	Q-1					
				Q-1		
		Q-2				
Q-3						

If we now try to turn the table (Fig. 1.2) on another side, you can see Q-0 in the central column, we notice that the movements are always 6 on the right and 6 on the left, 12 total.

Fig. 1.2

					Q-2	
			Q-0			
	Q-2					
						Q-3
				Q-1		
		Q-1				
Q-3						

The same thing is valid for a chess board of even number, for example 4x4 (Fig. 1.3), the only difference is this:

$4 \times 4 = 16$, $16/2 = 8$, $8/2 = 4$, then 2 movements for each side of the board, but the important thing to consider is Q-1 Sup. = Q-0 and therefore only Q-2 moves of 2 spaces and Q-1 Low. of 1 space, total 3 spaces, and the same thing applies if Q-1 Low. = Q-0 and consequently only Q-2 moves 2 spaces and Q-1 Sup. of 1 space, total 3 spaces.

Fig. 1.3

		Q-2	
Q-1 Sup.			
			Q-1 Low.
	Q-2		

Conclusions

So in conclusion if we tried to put queens on a chessboard we must consider that each side of the board has the same empty spaces of another side for the following formula $n \times n = N1 / 8 = N2$ number of displacements on each side by Q-0 (Q-0 = the central row or column of the chessboard), of all the chessboard queens.

Bibliography

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[2] John Watkins, *Across the Board: The Mathematics of Chess Problems*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2004.